

Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Co³⁺ and Fe³⁺ Chelates of N,N'-Isopropylene-bis-(2-OH, 3-Br, 5-Me-Benzophenoneimine)

R. B. PATEL

(Government College, Daman)

Manuscript received 6 March 1981, revised 24 August 1982, accepted 10 December 1982

The Schiff base N,N'-isopropylene-bis-(2-OH, 3-Br, 5-Me-benzophenoneimine) is used to study its complex forming behaviour with copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II), cobalt(III) and iron(III) ions. A square planar structure for the bivalent metal complexes has been assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, molecular weight determination, conductivity, magnetic moment, electronic spectra and TGA, DTA.

WE had earlier reported the stereochemical studies of transition metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from *o*-hydroxy-ketophenones and hexamethylenediamine¹ and butylnediamine². Syamal *et al*³ have observed that the stereochemistry of Co(II) complexes are affected by the nature of diamines used for obtaining the Schiff base ligands. The present communication deals with the synthesis and characterization of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Co(III) and Fe(III) complexes of N,N'-isopropylene-bis-(2-OH, 3-Br, 5-Me-benzophenoneimine).

Experimental

Preparation of Schiff base: Two moles of 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl-benzophenone and one mole of isopropylenediamine were refluxed in presence of absolute ethanol on a water bath for about 30 min. The yellow precipitates of Schiff base were filtered and washed with 50% alcohol to remove excess of bromoketone and finally dried and crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 176°.

Preparation of chelates: The solid Schiff base and ethanolic buffered metal ion solution of copper, nickel, cobalt or iron were refluxed on water bath for 2 hr. The Co(II) chelate was prepared under reducing atmosphere of hydrogen. Co(III) chelate was prepared after oxidising cobalt(II) to cobalt(III) by H₂O₂ and NaOH. The light green, yellow, dark yellow, greenish yellow and brownish red precipitates of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Co(III) and Fe(III) chelates, respectively were filtered and washed with water, dried at room temperature and crystallised from chloroform. The chelates are soluble in chloroform and DMF.

Analytical: All the five chelates were decomposed by perchloric acid and the metal ions were estimated by standard methods⁴⁻⁶. The molecular weights⁷, determined cryoscopically using camphor as a solvent, showed monomeric nature. The conductivity⁸ of the chelates measured

in DMF on a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge indicate their non-electrolytic nature. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. DTA was carried out on a Schreiber type 05174 220v 5H₂ instrument at CSMCRI* to find the presence of water molecule and TGA was carried out on a Cambridge Clearspan P250L thermobalance to study the thermal stability of Co³⁺ and Fe³⁺ complexes. The results of several such determinations are represented in Table 1.

The structure of the divalent and trivalent metal chelates can be depicted as below:

Magnetism: The magnetic susceptibility of the chelates was determined on a Gouy balance at room temperature. The calculated values for magnetic moments of Cu(II) and Co(II) chelates are 1.903 and 1.84 B.M., respectively indicating one unpaired electron while the Ni(II) chelate was diamagnetic. Co(III) and Fe(III) chelates had magnetic moment of 0.58 and 6.09 B.M., respectively. The low magnetic moment value for Co(III) complex is due to TIP and indicates a t_{2g}⁶ configuration. The Fe(III) complex is a high spin octahedral complex. These data suggest square planar structure for copper(II), nickel(II) and Co(II) complexes and an octahedral structure^{9,10} for cobalt(III) and iron(III) chelates.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the five chelates were recorded on Spectronic-20. The solvent used was chloroform. The electronic

* Central Salt and Marine Chemical Research Institute, Bhavnagar.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Chelate	Molecular formula	Found (Calcd.)				mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹	B.M.	Electronic spectra		
			Mol. wt.	Element metal	Percentage N	Percentage Br			λ	ϵ	Assignment
1.	CuSB	(C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₂)Cu	658 (681.54)	9.127 (9.326)	3.327 (3.816)	23.12 (23.28)	15	1.903	610 (108) 560 (220) 400 (5850)	² B _{1g} → ² A _{1g} ² B _{1g} → ² E _g Intraligand	
2.	NiSB	(C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₂)Ni	671 (676.71)	8.342 (8.656)	3.561 (3.843)	23.90 (23.65)	10	dia	600 (400) 540 (900) 410 (4900)	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g} ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ E _g Intraligand	
3.	CoSB	(C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₂)Co	666 (676.94)	8.610 (8.708)	3.789 (3.842)	23.38 (23.64)	15	1.84	660 (350) 520 (2640) 410 (7250)	² A _{1g} → ² B _{1g} ² A _{1g} → ² E _g Intraligand	
4.	CoSB(H ₂ O)Cl	(C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₂ Cl)Co	722 (730.44)	7.615 (8.071)	4.121 (3.838)	23.91 (23.91)	2	0.38	530 (103) 490 (500) 390 (2200)	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{1g} ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g} Intraligand	
5.	FeSB(H ₂ O)Cl	(C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₂ Cl)Fe	718 (727.35)	7.810 (7.679)	3.576 (3.386)	22.00 (23.515)	3	6.09	—	—	

spectra of Fe³⁺ chelate show a general and increasing absorption spectrum and very weak bands which are difficult to interpret. Their weakness, however, is as expected because the transitions are spin forbidden as well as are forbidden by Laporte rule.

DTA and TGA: To confirm whether water is in the complex, DTA was carried out. The graph of complexes show distinct endothermic peaks from 90 to 200°. These endothermic peaks are indicative of the presence of water. To study the thermal stability, TGA¹¹ was carried out. The following are the results.

Chelates	% wt loss of water at 190-200°		% wt of the residue	
	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
Co ³⁺ SB(H ₂ O)Cl	2.418	2.40	11.89	11.14
Fe ³⁺ SB(H ₂ O)Cl	2.984	3.10	10.11	10.00

IR spectra: The ir band at 3650 cm⁻¹ in the ligand is found to be absent in the complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) ions. A broad band in the ir spectra of Co(III) and Fe(III) complexes indicate the presence of water. The (C=N) band in the ligand at 1630 cm⁻¹ is lowered to 1610-1620 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes indicating participation of the C=N group in complex formation. There is a distinct band at around 760 cm⁻¹ in Co(III) and at 765 cm⁻¹ in Fe(III) complexes indicating

water rocking vibration. The (M-N) is found at 550 cm⁻¹ and (M-O) at 500 cm⁻¹.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks CSMCRI, Bhavnagar for facilities for magnetic moment and TGA, DTA measurements and Dr. L. D. Dave, Prof. of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University for helpful discussion.

References

1. R. B. PATEL, J. K. VERMA and R. K. SEVAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 472.
2. R. B. PATEL, *J. South Gujarat Univ.*, 1977, **6**, 170.
3. A. SYAMAL and V. D. GHANIKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 81.
4. CUMMING and KEY, "Quantitative Analysis" (Ed.) R. A. Chalmer, Oliver and Boyd Publishers, London, 1956, p. 257.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, 1969, p. 526.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, 1969, p. 529.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry (including Qualitative Analysis)", 3rd. Ed., Longmans, 1961, p. 103.
8. A. P. AMES and P. G. J. SEARS, *Phys. Chem. Ithaca*, 1955, **59**, 16.
9. A. EARNSHAW, "Introduction to Magnetochemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1968, p. 35.
10. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Wiley, 1966, p. 318.
11. A. VELRAIYAN and M. R. DUTTA, Abst., Ann. Conv. of Chemists, India, 1974.